

Restricted Rotation. Part—IV : Determination of Barrier to Rotation Around Some Crowded C-C and C-N Bonds by Dynamic Nuclear Magnetic Resonance

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Temperature dependence of the nmr spectra of a few typical methyl 2-aryl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enyl-acetates (I)-(VII) has been reinvestigated. The free energy, enthalpy and entropy of activation for the restricted rotation about the arylcyclohexenone bond have been determined by line shape analysis of the spectra of the side chain methylene protons using approximate equations. The free energy of activation for conformational inversion of the molecule (VII) is now found to be appreciably higher than that reported earlier although the result is still to be rationalised. The barrier energy around C-N bond in two 1-aryl-1,4-dihydro-4,4,6-trimethyl-2-thiopyrimidones (XIII) and (XV) has also been measured by dynamic nmr taking advantage of chemical nonequivalence of the geminal methyl groups and is found to be quite high (ca 98 kJ mol⁻¹).

SINCE its discovery, the high resolution nmr spectroscopy has become one of the most valuable tools of the chemists, biochemists and physicists for the determination of structures of molecules. In addition to the static aspects of the molecules (e. g., chemical shifts, coupling constants), nmr is capable of giving valuable information on many time-dependent phenomena which include a large number of exchange reactions characterised by certain rate constants¹. Rotation about a single bond may be visualised as an intramolecular stereodynamic process in which the rate constant depends on the barrier energy. Previously, molecules like biphenyls with restricted rotation around the pivotal bond had to be resolved into enantiomers in order to study the barrier energy and polarimetry was the sole method of investigation. Nowadays, it is possible to study the hindered rotation by means of the dynamic nmr when the energy barrier is just on the border line (75-96 kJ mol⁻¹), where compounds become too unstable to be isolated chemically, down to a barrier of 21-25 kJ mol⁻¹ below which another powerful tool, namely, microwave spectroscopy can be applied. Moreover, unlike polarimetry, it is not necessary that the two conformers should be enantiomeric and possess a chiral centre or axis. In principle², if a molecule by reason of restricted rotation happens to lack certain symmetry properties so that two conveniently placed groups (generally H or Me) become diastereotopic, the technique of dynamic nmr may be used to determine activation energies of the rotational process. A large number of biphenyl derivatives and their analogues have been studied using this method by various groups of workers³. In our laboratory, a dozen of 3-aryl-cyclohexenones of the type (I) have been synthesised

and the free energies of activation of restricted rotation about the arylcyclohexenone bond determined⁴⁻⁶ from the coalescence temperature of the AB-quartet of the diastereotopic protons in the acetate side chain. In the absence of full line shape analysis¹, the measurements were, however, confined to the calculation of free energies of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) for conformational inversion at the coalescence temperature (T_c). The significance of the values was limited by the fact that their temperature dependence was not known. In the present communication, a few typical molecules (I)-(VII) have been re-examined by line shape analysis using approximate equations, the enthalpy and entropy of activation have been calculated and compared, and the temperature dependence of free energies of activation has been studied. The compound (VII) which behaved atypically⁵ has been synthesised eliminating any controversy over its structure. In addition, the barrier to rotation about C-N bond in some 1-aryl-1,4-dihydro-4,4,6-trimethyl-2-thiopyrimidones⁷ has been determined by dynamic nmr.

Experimental

¹H NMR spectra at different temperatures were taken on a Varian EM390 90 MHz machine. Temperature control was provided by a Varian variable temperature controller with an accuracy of $\pm 2^\circ$. Temperatures above 50° were calibrated using the shift difference of an ethylene glycol sample. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm relative to TMS as internal standard. IR spectra were taken in CHCl₃ solution on Perkin-Elmer 237B spectrometer. Petroleum refers to a fraction, b.p. 40-60°. Organic solutions were dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. All

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I : R = OMe, R' = H

II : R = Me, R' = H

III : R = R' = Me

IV

V

VI

VII

VIII

IX

X

XI

XII

XIII : R = OMe

XIV : R = Me

XV : R = NO₂

the melting points are corrected. TLC was done on silica-gel plates using ethyl acetate and petroleum as eluents.

Methyl 2-aryl-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetates (I)-(VI) were prepared by method described earlier^{4,5}. The synthesis of compound (VII) has been carried

out with some modification as described below and the intermediates are carefully checked by tlc, glc and ¹H nmr for their purity.

1-Acetyl-2-methoxynaphthalene (VIII) : 1-Acetyl-2-methoxynaphthalene was prepared according to the previous method⁴ and was rigorously purified by

column chromatography (silica gel). It crystallised from petroleum in colourless plates, m.p. 58°; ^1H nmr spectrum (CDCl_3): δ 8.00-7.80 (3H, m, $3 \times \text{ArH}$), 7.60-7.20 (3H, m, $3 \times \text{ArH}$), 3.95 (3H, s, OCH_3) and 2.63 (3H, s, COCH_3); ν_{max} : 1695 and 1600 cm^{-1} . The ^1H nmr spectrum (CDCl_3) of 1-acetyl-2-naphthol⁸ is as follows: δ 13.55 (1H, s, exchangeable with D_2O , -OH), 8.17 (1H, d, $J=8 \text{ Hz}$, 8-H), 8.07-7.30 (4H, m, $4 \times \text{ArH}$), 7.20 (1H, d, $J=8 \text{ Hz}$, 3-H) and 2.87 (3H, s, COCH_3); ν_{max} : 1630 and 1580 cm^{-1} . Each of these compounds gave a single spot and a single peak in tlc and glc (FAAP 15% column), respectively.

Attempted preparation of 2-methoxy-1-naphthyl vinyl ketone (IX) with trifluoroacetic acid N-methyl-aniline salt (TAMA): Recently, a new procedure has been developed⁹ to synthesise α -methylene ketones using 'TAMA' and trioxymethylene. Accordingly, a mixture of 'TAMA' (2.25 g), 1-acetyl-2-methoxynaphthalene (2.00 g) and trioxymethylene (1.08 g) in dry freshly distilled dioxane (12 ml) was refluxed under N_2 for 2 hr followed by heating with fresh amount of trioxymethylene (0.51 g), 'TAMA' (1.2 g) and dioxane (6 ml) for 2 hr more. The ketone (VIII) was, however, recovered completely unchanged. Apparently, the method does not work with sterically hindered ketones⁹.

Methyl 7-(2-methoxy-1-naphthoyl)-4-oxoheptanoate (XI): This compound was prepared by condensing the Mannich base of 1-acetyl-2-methoxynaphthalene methiodide with ethyl β -oxo-adipate¹⁰ as described in a previous paper⁴. 2-Methoxy-1-naphthyl β -NN-dimethylaminoethyl ketone (X), prepared in the usual way had the ^1H nmr spectrum (CDCl_3): δ 8.05-7.70 (3H, m, $3 \times \text{ArH}$), 7.60-7.20 (3H, m, $3 \times \text{ArH}$), 3.97 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.13 (2H, s, COCH_2), 2.83 (2H, m, CH_2NMe_2) and 2.27 (6H, s, NMe_2); ν_{max} : 1695 and 1610 cm^{-1} . The dioxo-ester (XI) showed ^1H nmr (CDCl_3): δ 8.00-7.55 (3H, m, $3 \times \text{ArH}$), 7.50-7.20 (3H, m, $3 \times \text{ArH}$), 3.92 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.63 (3H, s, CO_2CH_3), 2.92 (2H, t, $J=7 \text{ Hz}$, 3-CH_2), 2.60 (6H, m, $3 \times \text{CH}_2\text{CO}$)

and 2.06 (2H, m, 6- H_2); ν_{max} : 1735 (CO_2Me), 1719 (satd. $\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1695 (ArCO) and 1610 cm^{-1} (aromatic). The dioxo-ester (XI) was a viscous gum, b.p. 220-225°/0.1 mm. Found: C, 70.3; H, 6.6. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 70.2; H, 6.4%.

Methyl 2-(2-methoxy-1-naphthyl)-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetate (VII): The above dioxo-ester (1.4 g; 4.1 mmol) was added to a solution of dry potassium *t*-amylate, prepared from potassium (0.16 g; 4.1 mmol), in benzene (30 ml). The solution was refluxed on a water-bath for 5 hr under N_2 . Some salt precipitated out. The cooled mixture was decomposed with dilute acid and the organic matter was extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed repeatedly with aqueous NaHCO_3 solution when 2-(2-methoxy-1-naphthyl)-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetic acid (hydrolysed from the cyclised ester by the liberated water during aldol condensation) came up completely into the alkaline layer. On acidification, a gum (0.85 g) was obtained which was esterified with diazomethane and the ester sublimed at 200°/0.1 mm. The product was mostly methyl 2-(2-methoxy-1-naphthyl)-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetate (VII) admixed with a little amount (ca 20% as determined from nmr) of the methyl ether of the cyclopenta-1,3-dione derivative (XII) formed as a result of internal Claisen condensation. The product was chromatographed over silica-gel when the cyclohexenylacetate (VII) was obtained in crystalline form, m.p. 102° (from benzene petroleum). Found: C, 74.4; H, 6.7. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 74.1; H, 6.2%; ^1H nmr spectrum (CDCl_3): δ 8.00-7.31 (7H, m, ArH), 3.90 (3H, s, OCH_3), 3.42 (3H, s, CO_2CH_3), 3.00 (2H, AB-q, $\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{Me}$), 2.65 (4H, m, 3- H_2 +5- H_2) and 2.26 (2H, m, 4- H_2). In $\text{C}_6\text{D}_6\text{NO}_2$, the side chain quartet at δ 3.00 appeared as a singlet but in CDCl_3 (up to 60°) and in $\text{Cl}_2\text{C}=\text{CCl}_2$, the quartet was retained.

The ester formed a red dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 216° (reported⁵ m.p. 216-217°). Found: C, 62.1; H, 5.1; N, 11.0. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_4\text{O}_7$ requires C, 61.9; H, 4.8; N, 11.1%; ^1H nmr spectrum

TABLE 1—NMR PARAMETERS^a AND ENERGIES^b OF ACTIVATION OF ROTATION ABOUT THE ARYL-CYCLOHEXENONE BOND IN COMPOUNDS (I)-(VII)

Compound	Solvent	J_{AB} Hz	$\Delta\nu_{AB}$ Hz	T_0 °C	k_0	ΔG_0^\ddagger	$\Delta G_0^{\ddagger\circ}$	k_{100°	ΔG_{100°	k_{180°	$\Delta G_{180^\circ}^\ddagger$	ΔH^\ddagger	ΔS^\ddagger e.u.
I	$\text{C}_6\text{D}_6\text{NO}_2$	15.00	16.10	45	89.15	66.05	67.80	630	71.90	—	—	50.24	-11
	$o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$	24.00	25.88	50	142.60	64.08	—	620	72.00	—	—	46.00	-13
II	$\text{C}_6\text{D}_6\text{NO}_2$	16.50	17.43	145	97.80	87.45	88.41	—	—	700	87.60	95.14	+4
III	$\text{C}_6\text{D}_6\text{NO}_2$	16.50	17.43	145	97.80	87.50	88.60	—	—	710	87.66	96.39	+5
IV	$\text{C}_6\text{D}_6\text{NO}_2$	17.00	20.98	62	110.40	69.10	69.80	640	71.80	—	—	52.67	-12
V	$\text{C}_6\text{D}_6\text{NO}_2$	16.50	19.45	184	99.70	95.85	95.30	—	—	—	—	—	—
VI	$\text{C}_6\text{D}_6\text{NO}_2$	17.00	40.60	95	129.20	75.49	75.80	380	76.20	—	—	65.25	-6
VII	$\text{Cl}_2\text{C}=\text{CCl}_2$	17.00	10.50	80	95.50	73.15	66.00	160	74.17	—	—	53.50	-11

^aThe spectral changes are reversible with temperature. ^bEnergy is expressed in kJ mol^{-1} ; the maximum errors are estimated for ΔG^\ddagger to be $\pm 1.0 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$; for ΔH^\ddagger to be $\pm 4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, and for ΔS^\ddagger to be $\pm 4 \text{ e.u. mol}^{-1}$. ^cData taken from refs. 5, 6.

(CDCl₃) : δ 11.2 (1H, s, ArNH), 9.23 (1H, d, J=3 Hz, 3'-ArH), 1.60 (1H, 2×d, J=9 and 3 Hz, 8-ArH), 8.10-7.30 (7H, m, ArH), 3.94 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.50 (3H, s, CO₂CH₃), 3.17 (2H, AB-q, J=17 Hz, Δν=10 Hz, CH₂CO₂Me), 2.80 (2H, t, J=7 Hz, 5-H₂), 2.60 (2H, t, J=7 Hz, 3-H₂) and 2.24 (2H, m, 4-H₂).

1-Aryl-1,4-dihydro-4,4,6-trimethyl-2-thiopyrimidones (XIII)-(XV): These thiones were prepared by a one step procedure from the corresponding aromatic amines, 4-methylpent-3-en-2-one (mesityl oxide), ammonium thiocyanate, water and hydrochloric acid as reported^{11,12}. These compounds have been characterised by us (ir, nmr) elsewhere⁷.

Results and Discussion

The nmr spectra of the seven arylcyclohexenones (I)-(VII) showed an AB-quartet (first three lines were clearly discernible in all the spectra) for the diastereotopic methylene protons of the acetate side chain. The J_{AB} and Δν values were calculated from the positions of the first and second, and first and third lines respectively according to standard procedure⁵. At coalescence temperature (T_c), each quartet coalesced to a broad singlet which gradually sharpened with increased temperature. The approximate exchange rate, k_c, and the free energy barrier to configurational inversion, ΔG[‡], at T_c were calculated by using equations (1) and (2), respectively¹³. At several temperatures above T_c, the line widths of the coalesced singlet at its half height (W/Hz) were measured and the approximate inversion rates were obtained over a range of temperatures by equation (3)^{14,15} where W₀ is the half width of the singlet at the highest temperature attainable. When k was plotted against 1/T (T in absolute scale), an approximate linear relationship

$$k_c = \pi[(\Delta\nu_{AB}^2 + 6J_{AB}^2)/2]^{1/2} \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\Delta G_c^\ddagger = 4.57 \times T_c (10.32 + \log \frac{T_c}{k_c}) \quad \dots (2)$$

$$k = \frac{\pi \Delta\nu_{AB}^2}{2(W - W_0)} \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\Delta H^\ddagger = E_a - RT \quad \dots (4)$$

$$\Delta S^\ddagger = \frac{\Delta H^\ddagger - \Delta G^\ddagger}{T} \quad \dots (5)$$

was observed which permitted the determination of the values of ΔG[‡] at different temperatures with some degree of accuracy. Arrhenius parameter, E_a, was measured from the slope of the straight line when log k was plotted against 1/T and from E_a, ΔH[‡] and ΔS[‡] were calculated using equations (4) and (5). The results are summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 2—NMR PARAMETERS^a AND FREE ENERGIES OF ACTIVATION OF ROTATION ABOUT C-N IN COMPOUNDS (XIII) AND (XV)

Compound	Solvent	Δν Hz	T _c °C	k _c	ΔG [‡] kJ mol ⁻¹
XIII	C ₆ D ₅ NO ₂	1.5	140	3.33	97.90±0.2
	<i>o</i> -C ₆ H ₄ Cl ₂	2.4	150	5.33	98.73±0.2
XV	C ₆ D ₅ NO ₂	3.0	160	6.67	100.24±0.2

^aThe spectral changes are reversible with temperature.

It may, however, be noted that the enthalpy and entropy of activation derived from nmr line shape analysis using approximate equations are subject to large systematic errors¹⁶. Consequently, the significance of the values of ΔH[‡], ΔS[‡] and the observed temperature dependence of ΔG[‡] are very much doubtful and no serious conclusion should be drawn therefrom. The following points are observed from the results presented in Table 1 which also contains data of our previous work⁵ for comparison.

i) The coalescence temperature, T_c, and free energy of activation, ΔG[‡], of the 2-methoxy-1-naphthyl derivative (VII) have now considerably increased. The former is found to be 80° instead of 45° and the latter 73.15 instead of 66.00 kJ mol⁻¹, determined in tetrachloroethylene. The AB-quartet remained intact in chloroform solution upto 60° which shows that the previous measurement (done in a foreign laboratory) was wrong. The ΔG[‡] value (73.15 kJ mol⁻¹) is still very much less than that (95.30 kJ mol⁻¹) for the 1-naphthyl-derivative (V). We reiterate our previous explanation⁵ that the ground state energy of the molecule (VII) is appreciably increased by the *o*-methoxy substituent while that of the transition state may have been reduced by a combined effect of conjugation and out-of-plane bending of the pivotal bond both assisted by methoxyl group^{17,18}. It must be understood that unlike the biphenyl derivatives, where both the rings are planar, the cyclohexenone moiety in VII is nonplanar and may have different conformations in the ground and the transition states leading to different steric interactions. The ΔG[‡] values of the rest of the compounds agreed with those previously reported⁵.

ii) Although the measurement of ΔH[‡] and ΔS[‡] values are very much unreliable for reasons stated earlier, there is an unmistakable trend towards high negative entropy of activation (-11 e.u.) and low ΔH[‡] values for compounds (I), (IV) and (VII) which contain an *ortho*-methoxyl group. On the other hand, the three compounds (II), (III) and (V) having no methoxyl substituent show very small (almost negligible) positive entropy of activation and their ΔH[‡] values are comparable with those of ΔG[‡]. It is risky to draw any firm conclusion based on this very uncertain ground; we can only conjecture that the rotation of the methoxyl group *ortho* to the pivotal bond is much more restricted (and therefore more orderly) in the transition state than in the ground

state, which explains this negative entropy of activation. Alternatively, one can argue that for compounds having relatively low coalescence temperatures, the systematic error for the determination of the enthalpy and entropy of activation is much greater than for compounds having high coalescence temperatures. This is, however, not borne out from the experiments of Oki *et al*¹⁴ on 5,7-dihydrobenzo-[c,e] thiopyins having low coalescence temperatures.

iii) The temperature dependence of ΔG^\ddagger also presents some inconsistency between the two series of compounds. Thus while for the non-methoxylated compounds (II), (III) and (VI), the ΔG^\ddagger values at T_c , 100° and 180° are fairly constant, for the methoxylated compounds (I), (IV) and (VII), the ΔG^\ddagger values vary appreciably with temperature. This is, of course, expected from the difference in the entropy of activation in the two series. Comparison of the ΔG^\ddagger values at coalescence temperatures, therefore, may not be a true index of the relative restricted rotation in this series. The values are to be taken qualitatively rather than quantitatively.

Three 1-aryl-1,4-dihydro-4,4,6-trimethyl-2-thiopyrimidones (XIII)-(XV) were studied by dynamic nmr technique. The two rings connected by a C-N bond are dissymmetrically substituted and so if the bond are rotation about this bond is sufficiently restricted by *ortho*-substitution in the phenyl ring, the two geminal methyl groups at C-4 might be chemically nonequivalent and would appear as a doublet. This happens to be the case for compounds (XIII) and (XV), the two 4-methyl groups giving two signals around δ 1.40 with small $\Delta\nu$ values (1.5-3.0 Hz) depending to some extent on the solvents used (see Table 2). In these two cases, the inversion rate, k_o , at T_c was determined by equation (6)¹⁸ and then the free energy of activation was obtained by substituting the value of k_o in equation (2). The ΔG^\ddagger values range between 97.90 and 100.24 kJ mol⁻¹ which are little higher than the energy barriers to rotation about C-N bond in 1-arylhydantoin²⁰ and N-arylsuccinimides²¹ in which six-membered thiopyrimidone ring is replaced by similarly constituted five-membered one.

$$k_o = \frac{\pi \Delta\nu}{\sqrt{2}} \quad \dots (6)$$

The almost equal values of ΔG^\ddagger for the compounds (XIII) and (XV), inspite of the fact that nitro group is much bulkier than methoxyl, is certainly due to resonance stabilisation of the transition state in the latter. Since the chemical shift difference is very small, the line shape analysis by taking the spectra at different temperatures would not have helped much. In the case of *o*-methyl compound (XIV) and of a few more similar com-

pounds⁷, the differential aromatic ring anisotropy is not strong enough to cause any chemical shift difference in the geminal methyl groups situated at the other end of the molecule.

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